

TREATMENT OF DOUBLE STARS IN THE OVERALL NDAC DATA PROCESSING †

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ABSTRACT. Four phases of the double-star treatment by the Northern Data Analysis Consortium (NDAC) are described. (1) Accumulation of various goodness-of-fit measures for all programme stars as part of the regular processing. (2) Critical examination of the measures at the end of the mission and cross-checking with duplicity information in the Input Catalogue results in a list of 10-15,000 'trouble stars', i.e. known or suspected non-single stars. (3) Compilation of a 'case history file' for each trouble star by extraction of all relevant information from intermediate data files. (4) Detailed analysis of each object by non-linear least-squares fitting of different object models.

1. INTRODUCTION

The Hipparcos instrument and the 'regular' (main chain) data processing are basically designed to handle point sources whose motions are adequately described by the standard five astrometric parameters. This defines what we call single stars. Other objects (except solar-system bodies) constitute the trouble stars: known or unknown double and multiple stars, and stars systematically disturbed by veiling glare. This paper describes the special treatment required by trouble stars. In order of decreasing priority, the aims of that treatment are:

- to prevent propagation of model errors to the 90% single stars. This is achieved by employing robust methods of estimation and by not using identified trouble stars in critical processes like the attitude reconstitution, instrument calibration, and sphere reconstitution;

- to get good astrometric data (positions, parallaxes, and proper motions referred to the primary or photocentre) also for visual double and multiple stars and for single stars disturbed by veiling glare;

- to derive relative information for their components;

- to discover new double and multiple stars.

2. ACCUMULATION OF GOODNESS-OF-FIT STATISTICS

Deviations from the single-star model show up as a lack of fit when analyzing the IDT and starmapper signals, and in the determination of the astrometric parameters. As part of the regular processing, certain

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goodness-of-fit statistics derived from these processes will be accumulated. The analysis of the starmapper signal is not described here, although the resolution of multiple starmapper transits could be an important way to get positional data on wide binaries ($\rho > 0.8''$).

2.1. Analysis of the IDT signal

The standard 5-parameter model fitted to the IDT photon counts is

$$N_{\ell} \sim \beta_1 + \beta_2[\cos(H_{\ell} + \beta_3) + \beta_4 \cos 2(H_{\ell} + \beta_3) + \beta_5 \sin 2(H_{\ell} + \beta_3)] \quad (1)$$

where N_{ℓ} is the photon count for the ℓ th sample and H_{ℓ} a reference phase defined relative to the frame mid-time (increasing if the satellite spins in the nominal sense). A binning algorithm using unweighted least-squares determination followed by one Maximum Likelihood iteration is used to estimate the signal parameters $\underline{\beta} = (\beta_1 \beta_2 \beta_3 \beta_4 \beta_5)'$ and their 5x5 covariance matrix $\underline{C}$. Note that (1) is valid for any type of object, single or not; the major modelisation errors are the neglected third harmonic and photocathode non-uniformity.

If M_1 , M_2 are the modulation factors and v the phase of the second harmonic with respect to the first, we have for a single star

$$E(\beta_4) = (M_2/M_1) \cos v, \quad E(\beta_5) = (M_2/M_1) \sin v \quad (2)$$

M_1 , M_2 , and v depend on the star colour, the position in the field, and on long-term variations of the instrument (abrupt changes are expected after refocussing). Using the majority of single stars, calibration values $\tilde{\beta}_4$, $\tilde{\beta}_5$ can thus be derived as functions of colour, field coordinates, and time. Deviation of observed β_4 , β_5 from the calibration values may indicate a trouble star, since the superposition of two or more single-star modulations does not in general preserve the amplitude and phase relations between the harmonics. A suitable measure of the deviation is the statistic

$$\Delta\chi^2 = \underline{\Delta\beta}' \underline{C}^{-1} \underline{\Delta\beta}, \quad \underline{\Delta\beta} = (0, 0, 0, \beta_4 - \tilde{\beta}_4, \beta_5 - \tilde{\beta}_5)' \quad (3)$$

which is computed for all observations. For single stars, $\Delta\chi^2$ is approximately chi-square distributed with 2 degrees of freedom. The transformed statistic $-2\ln(\Delta\chi^2)$ is then uniformly distributed in $[0, 1]$. We take advantage of this simple result by accumulating, for every programme star, a histogram of the integer variable

$$h = \text{INT}[8\exp(-\frac{1}{2}\Delta\chi^2)], \quad 0 \leq h \leq 7 \quad (4)$$

(Fig. 1). Under the null hypothesis that the star is single (i.e. that the observed β_4 , β_5 generally agree with the calibration values) the histogram should be flat. Trouble stars tend to give more frames with large $\Delta\chi^2$ (small h), thus producing a skewed histogram. The histogram is quite insensitive to occasional very large $\Delta\chi^2$, as caused e.g. by veiling glare from the other FOV.

Fig. 1. Simulated histograms of the statistic h [eqn (4)] for 100 frames with random orientation (θ). The object is a double star with B-magnitudes 11 and 12 and separation ρ varying from 0 to 15". The binary would have been detected from such a histogram if $\rho > 0.25''$.

2.2. Determination of astrometric parameters

Current catalogue values of the astrometric parameters (α , δ , Π , μ_α , μ_δ) are corrected by least-squares solution of equations like

$$c_1 \Delta\alpha + c_2 \Delta\delta + c_3 \Delta\Pi + c_4 \Delta\mu_\alpha + c_5 \Delta\mu_\delta + v = a_{\text{obs}} - a_{\text{cat}} \quad (5)$$

where c_1 to c_5 are known coefficients, a_{obs} the abscissa obtained in the great-circle reduction (corrected for the RGC zero point error) and a_{cat} the abscissa calculated from the current catalogue parameters. The noise v is assumed to have a standard deviation σ_a as estimated in the great-circle reduction. After adjustment, the statistic

$$\chi^2 = \sum_{\text{RGC's}} \left[\frac{a_{\text{obs}} - a_{\text{cat}}}{\sigma_a} \right]^2 \quad (6)$$

should then have a chi-square distribution with $n-5$ degrees of freedom (n = number of RGC's used in the solution). Abnormally large χ^2 could be due to slit errors (one or several a_{obs} wrong by an integer multiple of 1.208"), veiling glare from the other FOV causing spurious large abscissa errors, or underestimation of σ_a . Suitable measures must be taken to eliminate such trivial causes: slit errors are resolved by routinely making a mesh search around the expected position; a rejection technique is used to handle occasional outliers;

the formal mean errors might be re-scaled after statistical analysis. Remaining cases of large χ^2 are attributed to trouble stars.

3. IDENTIFICATION OF TROUBLE STARS

At the end of the mission, when all the data have gone at least once through the whole process up to the determination of astrometric parameters, a list of perhaps 10-15,000 trouble stars is set up. A programme star is put on this list if it has a duplicity or veiling glare flag in the Input Catalogue [according to some criterion $\Delta m < f(m_H, \rho)$], if the histogram of $\Delta\chi^2$ is significantly skew, or if the χ^2 from the astrometric parameters fit is large. Note that the three sources are to some extent complementary, as for instance astrometric binaries might be discovered from χ^2 but not from $\Delta\chi^2$. For checking purposes the list will also include a small random sample of programme stars which did not raise a flag in any of the processes, and some assuredly single stars. Their detailed analysis will hopefully lead to the conclusion that they are indeed single.

4. COMPILATION OF CASE HISTORY FILES

4.1. Intermediate results: FOV crossing data

The detailed analysis of trouble stars basically uses the IDT signal parameters β as 'observations'. These data, which are normally just converted to grid coordinates and passed on to the great-circle reduction, must therefore be saved for the trouble stars. But since these are not definitely identified until after the mission is completed, we have to save the IDT parameters for all programme stars. To keep storage at a reasonable level, a compressed form is computed by averaging over the 9-10 consecutive frames of a FOV crossing.

The observed parameters β_4 and β_5 are first corrected for known variations of M_2/M_1 and v with colour, field coordinates, and time. These variations are known from the calibration values $\tilde{\beta}_4, \tilde{\beta}_5$ computed for every frame (Section 2.1). The 'rectified' parameters, corresponding to an ideal instrument with fixed modulation ratio $R = M_2/M_1$ and no phase error ($v = 0$) for point sources, are

$$\bar{\beta}_4 = (R/\tilde{R}^2) (\tilde{\beta}_4\beta_4 + \tilde{\beta}_5\beta_5), \quad \bar{\beta}_5 = (R/\tilde{R}^2) (\tilde{\beta}_4\beta_5 - \tilde{\beta}_5\beta_4) \quad (6)$$

with $\tilde{R}^2 = \tilde{\beta}_4^2 + \tilde{\beta}_5^2$. Weighted averages of $\beta_1, \beta_2, \bar{\beta}_4, \bar{\beta}_5$ are computed for ten consecutive frames covering the FOV crossing. A sum of the information matrices $\bar{F}_\beta = C^{-1}$ is also computed, and the weights are taken proportional to $(\bar{F}_\beta)_{33}$. The output data per FOV crossing are:

- the star identification number;
- the mid-time of the first of the ten frames;
- the individual phases β_3 and relative weights of the frames;
- the mean signal parameters $\beta_1, \beta_2, \bar{\beta}_4, \bar{\beta}_5$;

- the upper-diagonal part of the total 5x5 information matrix.

These comprise 100 bytes per FOV crossing or ~ 2000 Mbytes in total.

4.2. Extraction and phase calibration

When the trouble stars have been identified, we loop through the FOV crossing data and extract the records concerned with these objects. Certain additional calculations are performed simultaneously with the extraction, using the final estimates of the attitude, field-to-grid transformations, and the RGC zero points now available. In particular, the (rectified and averaged) IDT signal is re-expressed in the form

$$N_{\ell} \sim b_1 + b_2 \cos\psi + b_3 \sin\psi + b_4 \cos 2\psi + b_5 \sin 2\psi \quad (7)$$

Here $\psi = 0$ (modulo 2π) at any time when a slit is exactly centred on a given reference point. The latter is defined by a fixed set of astrometric parameters $\alpha_0, \delta_0, \Pi_0, \mu_{\alpha 0}, \mu_{\delta 0}$ e.g. from the Input Catalogue. The procedure for calculating b_1 to b_5 is the following.

For given frame mid-time, calculate the proper direction $\underline{u}_0$ to the reference point by application of parallax, proper motion, gravitational light deflexion, and aberration. The attitude gives the orientation of the instrument triad $[\underline{x} \ \underline{y} \ \underline{z}]$ (Ref. 1) and hence the vector

$$\underline{w} = -\underline{x} f \sin(\gamma/2) + \underline{y} \cos(\gamma/2) \quad (8)$$

tangent to the instantaneous scanning circle ($\gamma =$ basic angle). The field index f and field coordinates w_0, z_0 of the reference point are

$$f = \text{sign}(\underline{y}'\underline{u}_0), \quad w_0 = \underline{w}'\underline{u}_0, \quad z_0 = \underline{z}'\underline{u}_0 \quad (9)$$

Applying the field-to-grid transformation [Ref. 2, eqn (3)] yields the grid coordinate $G_0 = G(f, w_0, z_0, B-V)$ such that a point source at the reference point would give $\beta_3 = 2\pi G_0$ (modulo 2π) in (1). Comparing with the observed value gives a phase difference

$$\Delta = \beta_3 - 2\pi G_0 \quad (\text{modulo } 2\pi) \quad (10)$$

which, apart from observation noise, should be constant over the FOV crossing. Averaging over the ten frames (signified by a bar) we have

$$\begin{aligned} b_1 &= \bar{\beta}_1 \\ b_2 &= \bar{\beta}_2 \overline{\cos\Delta}, & b_3 &= -\bar{\beta}_2 \overline{\sin\Delta} \\ b_4 &= \bar{\beta}_2 [\bar{\beta}_4 \overline{\cos 2\Delta} + \bar{\beta}_5 \overline{\sin 2\Delta}] \\ b_5 &= \bar{\beta}_2 [-\bar{\beta}_4 \overline{\sin 2\Delta} + \bar{\beta}_5 \overline{\cos 2\Delta}] \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

The information matrix is transformed accordingly,

$$\underline{F}_{-b} = (\partial \underline{\beta}' / \partial \underline{b}) \underline{F}_{-\beta} (\partial \underline{\beta} / \partial \underline{b}') \quad (12)$$

Some other mean quantities are also calculated at this stage (Section 5.2). The process requires only sequential access to the attitude and FOV crossing data, and the result is a sequential, chronological file of calibrated crossing data for the trouble stars of about 250 Mbytes.

4.3. The case history file

The final stage of the compilation process is to sort the phase calibrated FOV crossing data from chronological to starwise order into case history files. Each such file will be a comprehensive summary of all Hipparcos data needed to analyze a particular object or group of objects. Data for the components of wide binaries (which are separate entries in the Input Catalogue) and for programme stars mutually affected by veiling glare are combined in a single file, as they must be analyzed together. A tangential point for defining standard coordinates etc (Section 5.2) must be chosen near the centre of the configuration to be analyzed. The contents of a case history file are:

- (i) a running file number;
- (ii) equatorial coordinates of the tangential point (α_t, δ_t);
- (iii) m = number of Input Catalogue entries considered together;
- (iv) for each of the m entries ($i = 1$ to m):
 - running number in the Input Catalogue
 - number of components in the entry
 - CCDM number
 - reference point ($\alpha_0, \delta_0, \Pi_0, \mu_{\alpha 0}, \mu_{\delta 0}$)
- (v) n = number of FOV crossings;
- (vi) for each FOV crossing ($j = 1$ to n):
 - entry considered (i)
 - time of crossing (T)
 - mean position angle θ , frequency $2\pi/s$, and $\underline{w}'\underline{x}_t$
 - mean IDT Fourier coefficients b_1 to b_5
 - associated information matrix $\underline{F}_{-b}$ (upper diagonal)

The typical size is about 20 kbytes. The case history file may also be a convenient format to store Hipparcos data on those (hopefully very few) objects for which no reasonable or unambiguous solution can be found. It contains all the information needed to reconsider the solution e.g. in the light of new ground-based observations.

5. DETAILED ANALYSIS

5.1. Object models and fitting procedure

Two basic forms of object models are considered, using quite different parametrizations: the N-tuple star and the orbital binary.

N-tuple star ($N = 1, 2, 3, \dots$). This is specified by $6N$ parameters, namely the H-magnitude and astrometric parameters of the primary component ($H, x, y, \Pi, \dot{x}, \dot{y}$, where x and y are standard coordinates defined below), and the corresponding data for the remaining components expressed differentially with respect to the primary ($\Delta x, \Delta y, \Delta \Pi, \Delta \dot{x}, \Delta \dot{y}$). Constraints like $\Delta \Pi = 0$ (for a physical companion) and $\Delta \dot{x} = \Delta \dot{y} = 0$ (for relatively fixed components) may be imposed. For multiple IFOV pointings ($m > 1$ in the case history file) there are $m(m-1)/2$ additional parameters, viz. the mutual IFOV attenuation factors.

Orbital binary. This requires 15 parameters: $x, y, \Pi, \dot{x}, \dot{y}$ for the mass centre; $H, \Delta H$ and the mass ratio (q); the Thiele-Innes elements A, B, F, G for the size and orientation of the relative orbit; eccentricity (e), mean motion (dM/dT) and mean anomaly at the epoch J1990.0 (M_0). Determination of all of these parameters exclusively from Hipparcos data is of course impossible. Information from ground-based observations are needed in the form of an a priori parameter vector ($\underline{a}_0$) and associated information matrix ($\underline{F}_0$). Inclusion of Hipparcos data will then result in an improved parameter vector and weightier information matrix. Of particular interest is the possible determination of q for short-period binaries with well-determined orbits.

The object model specifies the motions $x_i(T), y_i(T)$ and intensities I_i (possibly attenuated by the IFOV factors) for the different components $i = 1$ to N . The resulting photon count model is

$$N_{\ell} \sim B + \sum_i I_i [1 + M_1 \cos(\psi + p_i) + M_2 \cos 2(\psi + p_i)] \quad (13)$$

where M_1, M_2 are conventional values for the modulation coefficients (with $R = M_2/M_1$) and p_i a phase difference computed from x_i, y_i (Section 5.2). The background B is a free non-negative parameter for each FOV crossing and not part of the object model. Equivalencing (7) and (13) we get the basic observation equations for a FOV crossing:

$$\begin{aligned} b_1 &= B + \sum_i I_i \\ b_2 &= M_1 \sum_i I_i \cos p_i, & b_3 &= -M_1 \sum_i I_i \sin p_i \\ b_4 &= M_2 \sum_i I_i \cos 2p_i, & b_5 &= -M_2 \sum_i I_i \sin 2p_i \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

A standard non-linear iterative least-squares adjustment of the model parameters ($\underline{a}$) is performed until the fit is satisfactory. The procedure seeks the global minimum of

$$s^2(\underline{a}) = (\underline{a} - \underline{a}_0)' \underline{F}_0 (\underline{a} - \underline{a}_0) + \sum_{\text{FOV's}} [\underline{b}(\underline{a}) - \underline{b}]' \underline{F}_b [\underline{b}(\underline{a}) - \underline{b}] \quad (15)$$

where $(\underline{F}_0, \underline{a}_0)$ represents the a priori information, $\underline{b}(\underline{a})$ the theoretical Fourier coefficients (14) and $\underline{b}$ the observed ones.

$s^2(\underline{a})$ is normally characterized by a multitude of local minima along the (x, y) and $(\Delta x, \Delta y)$ planes having separations of the order of a grid period. The iterative adjustment of $\underline{a}$ usually converges to the minimum nearest to the starting approximation. To ensure that the global minimum is found, one must try several starting approximations separated by not more than 0.5" in absolute or relative position. Introducing a priori information ($\underline{F}_0 > 0$) improves convergence by eliminating a lot of secondary minima, but will also bias the solution towards the a priori parameters. In the final iterations one should therefore modify $\underline{F}_0$ to include only information complementary to the Hipparcos data.

The results of extensive simulations of double- and multiple-star observations are reported in Ref. 3. That paper also gives further details on the detection and reduction techniques.

5.2. Definition of standard coordinates

The computation of p_i in (14) is facilitated by using special coordinates (x_i, y_i) for the coordinate directions to the stellar components. Differential equatorial coordinates like $(\Delta\alpha_i \cos\delta_i, \Delta\delta_i)$ are not suitable for this purpose, mainly because $\Delta\alpha$ is defined along a small circle. The (x, y) defined below resemble the standard coordinates (gnomonic projection) used in photographic astrometry (Ref. 4, Ch. 8.2), differing only by a scale factor taking into account differential aberration. This artifact makes it possible to work simply in coordinate directions instead of proper directions. As with ordinary standard coordinates, straight lines in (x, y) represent great-circle arcs on the sky.

Let $\underline{z}_t$ and $\underline{n}$ be unit vectors towards the tangential point (α_t, δ_t) and $\delta_t = 90^\circ$ respectively. The triad $[\underline{x}_t \ \underline{y}_t \ \underline{z}_t]$ with

$$\underline{x}_t = \langle \underline{n} \times \underline{z}_t \rangle, \quad \underline{y}_t = \underline{z}_t \times \underline{x}_t \quad (16)$$

defines an inertial system in which the arbitrary coordinate direction $\underline{c}$ can be expressed as

$$\underline{c} = (\underline{x}_t x + \underline{y}_t y + \underline{z}_t z) (1 + x^2 + y^2)^{-1/2} \quad (17)$$

with standard coordinates

$$x = \underline{x}_t' \underline{c} / \underline{z}_t' \underline{c}, \quad y = \underline{y}_t' \underline{c} / \underline{z}_t' \underline{c} \quad (18)$$

Specifically, the parallactic and proper motions of the reference point are given by the known functions $x_0(T)$, $y_0(T)$. The modulation phase depends however on the observed or proper direction to the star, differing from the coordinate direction by the gravitational deflexion and aberration. These effects were rigorously taken into account in the phase calibration for the reference point (Section 4.2). Therefore only the differential effects between the star and the reference point need to be considered here. Neglecting differential deflexion and using a first-order approximation for stellar aberration (Ref. 4, Ch. 2.5.4) the proper direction corresponding to $\underline{c}$ or (x, y) is

$$\underline{u} = \underline{c} (1 - \underline{c}'\underline{v}) + \underline{v} \quad (19)$$

where $\underline{v}$ is the barycentric velocity of the satellite divided by the speed of light. With subscript 0 always referring to the reference point we have

$$p/2\pi = G - G_0 \approx (\partial G/\partial w)(w-w_0) + (\partial G/\partial z)(z-z_0) \quad (20a)$$

$$w-w_0 = \underline{w}'(\underline{u}-\underline{u}_0) \approx \underline{w}'(\underline{c}-\underline{c}_0)(1 - \underline{c}_0'\underline{v}) \quad (20b)$$

$$z-z_0 = \underline{z}'(\underline{u}-\underline{u}_0) \approx \underline{z}'(\underline{c}-\underline{c}_0)(1 - \underline{c}_0'\underline{v}) \quad (20c)$$

$$\underline{c}-\underline{c}_0 \approx \underline{x}_t(x-x_0) + \underline{y}_t(y-y_0) + \underline{z}_t \frac{1}{2}[(x_0^2+y_0^2) - (x^2+y^2)] \quad (20d)$$

Defining an effective spatial frequency $2\pi/s$ and position angle of the scan θ by means of the following averages over the FOV crossing,

$$\begin{aligned} (2\pi/s)\sin\theta &= 2\pi \frac{(\partial G/\partial w)\underline{w}'\underline{x}_t + (\partial G/\partial z)\underline{z}'\underline{x}_t}{(\partial G/\partial w)\underline{w}'\underline{y}_t + (\partial G/\partial z)\underline{z}'\underline{y}_t} (1 - \underline{c}_0'\underline{v}), \\ (2\pi/s)\cos\theta &= 2\pi \frac{(\partial G/\partial w)\underline{w}'\underline{x}_t + (\partial G/\partial z)\underline{z}'\underline{x}_t}{(\partial G/\partial w)\underline{w}'\underline{y}_t + (\partial G/\partial z)\underline{z}'\underline{y}_t} (1 - \underline{c}_0'\underline{v}) \end{aligned} \quad (21)$$

we can finally write

$$p = (2\pi/s)[(x-x_0)\sin\theta + (y-y_0)\cos\theta] \quad (22)$$

The factor $(1 - \underline{c}_0'\underline{v})$ expresses the aberrational contraction/expansion of apparent images in the apex/antapex directions.

The quantities in (21) are actually computed already at the phase calibration stage (Section 4.2), as they involve the attitude ($\underline{w}$ and $\underline{z}$), orbital data ($\underline{v}$), and the field-to-grid transformation $G(f, \underline{w}, z, B-V)$. The principal error of the approximation (22) comes from neglecting the quadratic term in (20d) and is normally less than 0.1 mas within a radius of a few arcmin from the tangential point. This is sufficient for the double-star analysis but not for all cases of veiling glare correction. At greater separations, averaged FOV crossing data are probably not very useful for veiling glare correction anyway, due to the transverse attitude motion causing a variable phase difference between the stars as they move across the field. Thus it would seem appropriate to limit the case history file to objects within, say, 10 arcmin of the tangential point.

6. CONCLUSIONS

Two ideas have guided the design of the NDAC double star treatment. The first is not to rely on preconceived ideas about exactly what a 'trouble star' is or which programme stars belong to that category. Those things are best decided when a complete statistical picture of all the stars and observations emerges at the end of the mission. The type of information needed for this process and the crucial points at which it can be extracted are identified (Section 2).

The second idea is to collect all Hipparcos observations of a particular trouble star in a compact and fully self-contained form, without imposing any particular object model: the case history file. The further analysis of these data, by whatever method, can be done without reference to any other files (except the Input Catalogue Annex files for a priori data). It contains for instance all the input needed for the alternative 'image analysis' approach (Refs. 5, 6).

A beneficial and somewhat unexpected result is that veiling glare correction can be made within the same framework as the double star analysis, at least when the stars in question are within a radius of a few arcmin.

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